

Development of tools to optimise coordinated manure management and to improve soil fertilisation, crop quality and environmental protection

Summary

Development of innovative tools to optimise coordinated manure management and soil fertilisation from an economic and environmental point of view, within a joint and coordinated management framework, representative of the entire Catalan farming sector.

Objectives

To achieve sustainable and accurate manure management and soil fertilisation. To improve the efficiency of coordinated manure management. To enhance manure with regards to its fertilising content. To improve technological tools available for manure management and to adapt them to the needs of the Catalan farming cooperatives. To offer management and comprehensive advice by management centres. To reduce bureaucracy for the technicians of management centres.

Description of project activities

Implementation of: Fertilisation planning systems: analysis of soil and cultivation needs.
Tools to determine nutrient content of slurries (conductivity meter): to update and calibrate to each user/cooperative the relationship between the electric conductivity of the slurry and the nitrogen content.
Tools to improve efficiency in the application of organic fertilisers: regulation of flow volumes, standardising dosage and minimising emissions.
Tools to optimise transportation: to use software containing data of applications and of the fertilised plots.

Expected results and practical recommendations

To be able to enhance the fertilising content of slurry and to improve the available techniques to quantify the necessary parameters. To be able to set up a traceability system that will allow tracking the circuit of the slurry from farm to the land, containing all information and characteristics of the slurry, the plot and the crop. Through participation in this project, technicians of the cooperative will become familiar with the different implemented technologies (conductivity meter, GPS, software, etc.).

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Keyword-category

Animal husbandry and welfare
Fertilisation and nutrients management
Waste, by-products and residues man

Territorial scope

Province

Lleida
Girona
Barcelona

County

Pla d'Urgell
Osona
Noguera
Bages

Project dissemination (publications, seminars, multimedia...)

Project website

www.cooperativesagraries.cat

Other project information

Project period

Starting date (month-year): Maig 2017

End date (month-year):

Project status: *Ongoing*

Approved budget

Total budget: 247.500,00 €

Funding source DARP: 101.830,50 €

Funding source EU: 76.819,50 €

Own funds: 68.850,00 €

With the support of:

Project funded by Operation 16.01.01 (Cooperation for innovation) of the Rural Development Program of Catalunya 2014-2020.

Basic regulation: Ordre ARP/96/2016, de 27 d'abril, per la qual s'aproven les bases reguladores dels ajuts a la cooperació per a la innovació a través del foment de la creació de grups operatius de l'Associació Europea per a la Innovació en matèria de productivitat i sostenibilitat agrícoles i la realització de projectes pilot innovadors per part d'aquests grups, i es convoquen els corresponents a 2016.

Project id.: E+C 2016